

<p>ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN PRODUCTS SOLD IN THE NORTH MACEDONIAN MARKET</p>		<p>Linguistics</p> <p>Keywords: English language, Albanian language, North Macedonia, globalization, food products, music, cosmetic products, etc.</p>
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Abstract

English language is a foreign language for Macedonians as well as Albanians living in North Macedonia. It is a mandatory subject at school that students have to attend. In this way, English language cannot be compared to other foreign languages that people in North Macedonia may encounter. It is common to hear two or more young Albanian or Macedonian people speaking in English among themselves. They may use it as a secret code of speaking in spoken and written discourse, especially when using online platforms. Young people living in North Macedonia do not find it difficult to understand English words all around them; they even consider it a modern form of living. On the other hand, most of the older generations living in North Macedonia do not understand English. But nowadays, most people living in North Macedonia, regardless of their age, use technology and Internet and in this way they are already familiar with many English words, and they have also learnt their semantic function even without understanding the specific meaning of the words. The problem that is very often faced by most people is when buying specific products. After a short study, it was proved that almost in all products sold in different shops, even though they might be produced in North Macedonia, or in other countries in the Balkans, something or everything written on them is in English.

The Influence of English Language

Nowadays, English as a language of globalization has expanded its influence to various languages in the world, including Albanian language. The realization of effective communication and conveying specific meaning is one of the most important factors that influences on the increasing use of some English words. In the period known as the age of the internet and technology, a lot of English words are used among people and they often manage to expand their line of use by becoming part of various social discourses.

Xhevat Lloshi, emphasizes that globalization has caused Albanians to immerse themselves in the English environment. According to him, Albanians at home listen to English songs from Albanian groups named in English (West Side Family), watch Albanian TV programs titled in English (TopFest, Big Brother), they are surrounded in the street by English advertisements (Digitalb, Albsat), read newspapers with full English pages, even with English titles (Tirana Observer, Shoppingnë internet me njëklikimtëmausit), go to stores with English tables (open, close, Fastfood), buy products with English labels (baked rolls, Fanta-exotic), learn English in school and in courses, work with a computer with English programs (fajll, seju), or even state laws are drafted in English and then translated into Albanian.

As a result of globalization, some English words have replaced Albanian words such as: *sektor* and *katedër* are replaced with the word *departament*, *degë* with *division*, *kontroll-revizioni* with *auditim (audit)*, *ekzekutim* and *arritje* with *performancë*, etc.¹

When speaking about Albanian music, we witness an increasing number of unnecessary and uncontrollable anglicisms used in Albanian music needed for rhyme or rhythm, but their frequent listening causes them to enter without any control into everyday use among Albanian young generations. Ibrahim conducted a study and analyzed the lyrics of the songs from the annual festival “Këngamagjike” 2015-2016. From the top list of the 100 most listened entertaining songs she could provide examples and proved that Albanian music is ‘infected’ with English words and these words are then absorbed easily by young Albanian generations. Some of the words used in Albanian songs included: *man, king, nice, love, single, free, lady, body, jeans (xhinse), oh my God, money, bad boy, bye, text me, dance, party, queen*, etc.²

English Words in Product Advertisements

English words mostly dominate the mass media. This is an evidence of the global influence of the English language. English words, used for various phenomena, posters, electronic advertisements and enterprise logos, show the most visible manifestations of the global spread of English language. In addition to external advertising media, the phenomenon of the spread of anglicisms can be studied and elaborated in printed texts, including various types of promotional materials and print media. In these cases, English language is often used symbolically to create an image of something new, modern and dynamic. A study conducted in Finland on the use of English words to name local businesses confirmed their use in entrepreneurship such as: in fitness centers: *Blue Fitness, Fitness Club, City Gym, Move!, Wellness Center, Let’s go Center*; in a large number of hair salons: *Salon Hair, Cutting Club, Hair Art, Nice Cut, Hair Saloon, Top Hair*; in addition, restaurants with English names were numerous. English words were found in other fields as well, such as in companies where staff was required: *Office Help, Banquet Service, Businesslike, Star People and Manpower*; and in this list, frequent words such as *Center, Shop, Group, Service and Systems*³ could not be omitted. There is no need to say that all of the above English words listed by Kortmann and Auwera are encountered in North Macedonia. In fact, people in North Macedonia are already used to this reality.

Regarding product advertisement, after a survey of 2384 advertisements for women’s products in Belgium, France, Germany, the Netherlands and Spain, it was found that more than

¹ Xh.Lloshi, *Ndërhyrja e huazimeve nga anglishtja*, III International Seminar of Albanology – State University of Tetova, 2009, p. 28-31.

² B. Ibrahim, *Adaptimi i huazimeve angleze në tekstet e muzikës shqiptare*, Takimi i Parë Shkencor i Albanologëve të rinj – Sfidat e studimeve Albanologjike në fillim të shek. XXI, Tetovo, 2017, p. 101.

³ B. Kortmann, J. Auwera, *The Languages and Linguistics of Europe: A Comprehensive Guide*, De Gruyter Mouton, 2011, p. 611-612.

two-thirds of advertisements contained at least one English word, and thirteen percent of them were entirely in English⁴.

Speaking of the description of products used in households, in 40% of basic products that are part of every house in North Macedonia, after a survey made by us we could find products in which everything was written in Macedonian or Albanian (depending on the producer), or in both languages, but in 40% of them everything was written in English like: *fresh and beauty, dark chocolate sea shells, tomato spicy/hot ketchup, mild ketchup, made in China, free from artificial colors, gluten and artificial flavor enhances, guaranteed quality, nutrition's facts, no preservatives, traditional recipe, awarded Superbrand Macedonia's choice, 2 servings per container, serving size, Italian style, oven baked, chips, Mediterranean vegetables, dried, the best from mother Earth, all natural premium quality, spices and ingredients, dried fruits and nuts, Queen's Diamond*, etc. In 5% of the products, English was accompanied with words from other languages, whereas in 15% of the products, there were English words translated into Albanian or Macedonian such as the words: *tuna flakes in sunflower oil, cocoa spread with hazelnuts, sour milk, with peanuts, beef/chicken soup, goulash and stew, original taste, spaghetti, high quality rice, beans*.

Based on this study, it is surprising how it is possible in a country where no English people live (or they only live temporarily), 40% of basic food products are in English. In this way, it can be quite difficult for people who do not understand English to choose between different products with slight content differences. Photos on the products play a crucial role regarding this, but problems may arise very often because photos cannot solely substitute words that describe a certain ingredient or a certain specific of the product.

In order to carry out a comparative analysis regarding the influence of English language on various products, we have analyzed the words used in cosmetic and hygienic products found in our homes. When analyzing cosmetics and hygienic products that are used almost in every household, we found that in 85% of them everything was written in English, starting from the name of the products, their description and ingredients. We could find words like: *antibacterial hand gel, instant, mountain fresh, soft touch feeling, with lemon & betaines, liquid soap with provitamin B & natural extracts, anti-hair loss, silicone free, hair care formula, garlic shampoo, ph skin neutral, kids shampoo, shower gel, gentle and caring cleansing, mild formula, without artificial dyes, for sensitive skin, no silicones, shampoo, anti-yellow, young look, strong hair, shampoo against hair loss, for normal scalp, Naturals color crème, honey and argan oil, natural looking colors, intensively cared hair, alcohol and paraben free, 72 pcs, wet wipes, clean and soft, happy baby wipes, new!, premium quality, tested, intense repair, eco-friendly formula, vegan formula, very damaged hair, heat protection spray, advanced techniques, specially developed for*

⁴ Ibid, p.612, (citing: M. Gerritsen, C. Nickerson, V. D. C. Brandt, R. Crijns, N. Dominguez, F. Van Meursand U. Nederstigt, U. *English in print advertising in Germany, Spain and the Netherlands: Frequency of occurrence, comprehensibility and the effect on corporate image*. In *The use of English in International and Business Settings: An Intercultural Perspective*, G. Garzone & C. Ilie (eds), Bern: Peter Lang, 2007, p.293).

sensitive skin, advanced spectral technology, sun protection, anti-age cream, day/night cream, etc. Only 10% of the products had labels in Macedonian language as a translation of the English description, and only in 5% of them we could find areally short description in Albanian language as well.

Conclusion

With this study we were once again able to highlight that English language is part of our everyday life. English words were found in almost all products that could be found in our home. This proves that English as a global language is spreading very quickly among us. No matter how hard we try to avoid using English words, while being constantly surrounded by them, we also start using them consciously or unconsciously. In addition, not speaking English language may make it more difficult to buy some specific products in some situations. Sometimes it could be hard to understand what we buy without knowing at least some basic English and we may need to seek help from sellers or other people in order to buy specific products with labels only in English language, or with logos entirely in English language.

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